

A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Kgaswane Mountain Reserve, South Africa

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ABSTRACT

An annotated species list of spiders presently known from the Kgaswane Mountain Reserve in the North West province, South Africa, is provided. The checklist was compiled from data collected from the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa) database. A total of 222 species from 40 families and 152 genera are presently protected in the reserve. The most species-rich families are the Thomisidae (36 spp.), Salticidae (33 spp.) and Araneidae (26 spp.), while 11 families are represented by singletons. The global distribution, endemism, and conservation status for each species is provided. Ninety-eight percent of the species have a wide distribution range and are of Least Concern. Approximately 6.8% of the total South African spider fauna is protected in the reserve, and 19.8% of the species recorded are South African endemics.

Key words: South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa), conservation, endemism, Savanna Biome

INTRODUCTION

The South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa) was initiated in 1997 with the main aim to discover, describe, and make an inventory of the South African arachnid fauna. Species distribution data were essential information needed for the conservation assessments to compile a Red Data List of the Arachnida of South Africa. It is also important to have a record of endemic species, and species that are already receiving some protection in existing reserves and parks (McGeoch *et al.*, 2011).

The North West province covers 9.5% of the surface of South Africa. Only 2087 records of spiders from 89 sites are housed in the National Collection of Arachnida (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015) and large areas still need to be sampled. Some extensive sampling of spiders in North West were undertaken in conventionally cultivated cotton fields (Van den Berg *et al.*, 1990; Van den Berg & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1991; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 1999) where 31 families and 127 species were sampled. Data on all the arachnid orders in the SANSa database were used to prepare a report on the diversity of arachno-fauna in the North West province (Power, 2014).

To date, 380 spp. from 52 families are known from the province (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015). Very few large-scale surveys have been undertaken in the province, and the only long-term survey in the Kgaswane Mountain Reserve (KMR) is reported on here. The current study presents the results of data from the SANSa database on the spiders sampled in the KMR in the North West province. It includes information on the species' global distribution, endemism, and conservation status.

METHODS

Study area: The North West province lies in the north of South Africa on the Botswana border, fringed by the Kalahari Desert in the west, Gauteng province to the east, and the Free State province to the south. With a total area of 106 512 square kilometres, North West is the country's fourth smallest province, taking up 8.7% of South Africa's land area with a population of 3.5 million people.

Much of the province consists of flat areas of scattered trees and grassland. The Magaliesberg mountain range in the northeast extends about 130 km from Pretoria to Rustenburg.

Figures 1–2. 1. Entrance to the reserve. 2. Habitat at the Kgaswane Mountain Reserve (KMR). Photo credits: A.S. Dippenaar-Schoeman.

Magaliesberg Protected Natural Environment, about 100 km from Pretoria and Johannesburg. Originally established on the farm Rietvallei, which once belonged to President Paul Kruger, it has been gradually expanded over the years and now covers some 4500 ha. Temperatures range from 17 °C to 31 °C in the summer and from 3 °C to 21 °C in the winter. Annual rainfall totals about 360 mm, with almost all of it falling during the summer months, between October and April.

The reserve lies in the Savanna Biome, south-west of the town of Rustenburg. The land was proclaimed in 1967. It is situated on the northern slopes and summit of the Magaliesberg Mountain. The reserve is dominated by the rocky ridges of the Magaliesberg, with well-wooded ravines on the rugged slopes.

The Waterkloof River has its source here and runs through a reed basin. A large valley basin and an extensive plateau form an important water catchment area from which the main watercourse flows into a large, reed-filled marsh. Although broadly defined as sour bushveld, the reserve's vegetation is varied, comprising grassland, scrub, mixed woodland, and even scattered pockets of fynbos.

Sampling methods and identification: Spiders have been collected once a month over a period of four years from the KMR using beating, sweep-netting, and active search. The survey was monthly undertaken over a single day, therefore no pitfall traps were used. Sampling was done by members of the ARC Biosystematics' Arachnology team. Most samples were collected between 09h30 and 13h00. All the material collected has been deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA), Plant Health and Protection in Pretoria. The material was made available for taxonomic research, resulting in a large number of specimens being identified to species level.

FIGURE 3: Map showing location of the Kgaswane Mountain Reserve (KMR).

Species endemism and conservation: The conservation status of species is important, and as part of the first edition of the Spider Atlas (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2010), an endemism index was provided for each species. It was calculated based on current distribution, which included six endemism categories, ranging from: 6 = endemic, known only from type locality / one locality only (Kgaswane Mountain Reserve (KMRE)); 5 = known from North West province only, wider than type locality (NWE); 4 = known from two adjoining provinces only; 3 = South Africa, > two provinces or not adjoining (South African endemic, SAE); 2 = Southern Africa (south of Zambezi and Kunene Rivers) (Southern African endemic, STHE); 1 = Afrotropical Region (African Endemic, AE); 0 = Africa and wider (Cosmopolitan, C).

Regarding conservation status, species that were only recorded from immatures or those that represent possible new species or undetermined taxa were not evaluated (NE); species known from only one sex, old material, and not revised are data deficient either for taxonomic reasons (DDT) or lack distribution data (DD). Species with a broad distribution (categories 0–2) were considered to be of Least Concern (LC); those of categories 3–5 are South African endemics (SAE), and based on their distribution ranges, most of them are also LC. The species in categories 5–6 are North West endemics (NWE).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Numbers present: A total of 40 families represented by 152 genera and 222 species have been collected from KMR (Table 1; Appendix 1). These are the first published results of long-term surveys undertaken in the North West province. In this survey, the Thomisidae (36 spp.), Salticidae (33 spp.), and Araneidae (26 spp.) were the most species-rich families (Table 1). There was a very high proportion of singleton families (11), i.e., represented by a single species only.

TABLE 1: Spider diversity of the Kgaswane Mountain Reserve (KMR) with total number of families, genera (G) and species (S) sampled.

FAMILY	G	S	FAMILY	G	S
Agelenidae	2	2	Oxyopidae	3	9
Araneidae	19	26	Palpimanidae	1	1
Barychelidae	1	1	Philodromidae	4	7
Caponiidae	1	1	Pholcidae	2	2
Cheiracanthiidae	1	3	Phyxelididae	1	1
Clubionidae	1	1	Pisauridae	4	4
Corinnidae	4	4	Prodidomidae	1	3
Cyrtacheniidae	1	3	Salticidae	21	33
Deinopidae	1	1	Selenopidae	1	2
Dictynidae	1	1	Sicariidae	2	2
Entypesidae	1	1	Sparassidae	4	4
Eresidae	2	3	Tetragnathidae	2	4
Gallieniellidae	1	1	Theraphosidae	5	5
Gnaphosidae	11	20	Theridiidae	9	10
Hersiliidae	2	3	Thomisidae	18	36
Idiopidae	2	2	Trachelidae	2	2
Linyphiidae	3	3	Trochanteriidae	1	1
Lycosidae	7	8	Uloboridae	2	2
Migidae	1	1	Zodariidae	3	5
Oecobiidae	3	3			
Oonopidae	1	1	40 fam	152	222

Species endemism and conservation status: Of the 222 species sampled, 3 spp. (1.5 %) are data deficient (DD), i.e., lacking taxonomic or distribution data, while only one *Archaeodictyna* sp. (undetermined) was not evaluated (NE) (Table 2; Appendix 1). The majority of the species (217 spp., 98 %) sampled are listed as being of least concern (LC)

A large percentage of species have a wide distribution throughout Africa. A total of 22 spp. (9.8 %) are found in countries outside Africa; 104 spp. (46.8 %) are African endemics; 51 spp. (23 %) are endemics to Southern Africa, and only 44 spp. (19.8 %) are South African endemics.

There are presently no endemic species recorded from KMR and none of the species are North West endemics. Only *Paroecobius nicolai* Wunderlich, 1995 (Oecobiidae) (Fig. 18) is near endemic and has also been recorded from Limpopo and *Theuma schultzei* Purcell, 1908 (Prodidomidae) from Northern Cape. One of the species, *Evarcha flagellaris* Haddad & Wesolowska, 2011, collected at KMR, was listed as part of the type series.

TABLE 2: Conservation status and endemism of the spider species sampled at the the Kgaswane Mountain Reserve (KMR).

DISTRIBUTION	SPP.	%
CONSERVATION STATUS		
Data Deficient (DD)	3	1.5
Not Evaluated (NE)	1	0.5
Least Concern (LC)	217	98
Rare	0	
Near Threatened	0	
Vulnerable	0	
ENDEMICITY		
0 – Africa and wider (C)	22	9.9
1 – Africa endemics (AE)	104	46.8
2 – Southern African endemics (STHE)	51	23
3 – South African endemics (SAE)	44	19.8
4 – South African endemics (SAE): two adjacent provinces	3	1.4
5 – North West endemics (NWE)	0	0.5
6 – Kgaswane Mountain Reserve (KMR)	0	0

CONCLUSION

As signatories to the Convention on Biological Diversity, South Africa is obliged to develop a strategic plan for the conservation and sustainable utilisation of the diverse and species-rich fauna and flora. Preliminary investigations into the biodiversity of the invertebrate fauna in South Africa have highlighted the dilemma caused by a lack of baseline information on the ecology and diversity of most arachnid groups (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2002). Each survey contributes to our knowledge on the geographical distribution of spider species. Although this paper probably represents only a portion of the spider fauna present, we hope this information will stimulate further interest and research. The contribution of existing reserves can only be highlighted through studies such as this.

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FIGURE 4: Selected spiders from the Kgaswane Mountain Reserve (KMR). (4) *Pycnacantha tribulus* (Araneidae). (5) *Cyrtophora citricola* (Araneidae). (6) *Araneus apricus* (Araneidae). (7) *Eriovixia excelsa* (Araneidae). (8) *Neoscona theisi theisiella* (Araneidae). (9) *Gasteracantha sanguinolenta* (Araneidae). (10) *Misumenops rubrodecoratus* (Thomisidae). (11) *Hewittia gracilis* (Thomisidae). (12) *Tmarus foliatus* (Thomisidae). (13) *Pseudomicrommata longipes* (Sparassidae). (14) *Thyene natalii* (Salticidae). (15) *Cyrba boveyi* (Salticidae). (16) *Evarcha flagellaris* (Salticidae). (17) *Thanatus dorsilineatus* (Philodromidae). (18) *Uroecobius ecribellatus* (Oecobiidae) Photo credits: Peter Webb.

APPENDIX 1: Spiders of Kgaswane Mountain Reserve (KMR), listing their endemismity (END), conservation status (CON) and country endemismity (CEND).

FAMILY	END	CON	CEND	KNOWN SEX
1. Family Agelenidae				
<i>Benoitia ocellata</i> (Pocock, 1900)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Mistaria zuluana</i> (Roewer, 1955)	2	LC	STHE	B
2. Family Araneidae				
<i>Araneus apricus</i> Karsch, 1884	1	LC	AE	F
<i>Argiope australis</i> (Walckenaer, 1805)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Caerostris sexcupidata</i> (Fabricius, 1793)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Cyclosa insulana</i> (Costa, 1834)	0	LC	C	B
<i>Cyphalonotus larvatus</i> (Simon, 1881)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Cyrtophora citricola</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	0	LC	C	B
<i>Eriovixia excelsa</i> (Simon, 1889)	0	LC	C	B
<i>Gasteracantha sanguinolenta</i> C.L. Koch, 1844	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Kilima decens</i> (Blackwall, 1866)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Larinia bifida</i> Tullgren, 1910	1	LC	AE	F
<i>Mahembea hewitti</i> (Lessert, 1930)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Nemoscolus vigintipunctatus</i> Simon, 1897	2	LC	STHE	F
<i>Neoscona blondeli</i> (Simon, 1886)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Neoscona moreli</i> (Vinson, 1863)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Neoscona rapta</i> (Thorell, 1899)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Neoscona rufipalpis</i> (Lucas, 1858)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Neoscona subfusca</i> (C.L. Koch, 1837)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Neoscona theisi theisiella</i> (Tullgren, 1910)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Neoscona triangula</i> (Keyserling, 1864)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Pararaneus cyrtoscapus</i> (Pocock, 1898)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Poltys furcifer</i> Simon, 1881	1	LC	AE	F
<i>Prasonica seriata</i> Simon, 1895	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Pycnacantha tribulus</i> (Fabricius, 1781)	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Singa lawrencei</i> (Lessert, 1930)	1	LC	AE	F
<i>Trichonephila fenestrata</i> Thorell, 1859	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Trichonephila senegalensis annulata</i> (Thorell, 1859)	2	LC	STHE	B
3. Family Barychelidae				
<i>Pisenor arcturus</i> (Tucker, 1917)	2	LC	STHE	F
4. Family Caponiidae				
<i>Caponia spiralifera</i> Purcell, 1904	3	LC	SAE	B
5. Family Cheiracanthiidae				
<i>Cheiracanthium africanum</i> Lessert, 1921	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Cheiracanthium furculatum</i> Karsch, 1879	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Cheiracanthium vansoni</i> Lawrence, 1936	1	LC	AE	B
6. Family Clubionidae				
<i>Clubiona bevisi</i> Lessert, 1923	3	LC	SAE	B
7. Family Corinnidae				
<i>Apochinomma formicaeforme</i> Pavesi, 1881	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Cambalida dippenaarae</i> Haddad, 2012	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Copa flavoplumosa</i> Simon, 1885	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Corinnomma semiglabrum</i> (Simon, 1896)	1	LC	AE	B

FAMILY	END	CON	CEND	KNOWN SEX
8. Family Cyrtaucheniidae				
<i>Ancylotrypa brevipalpis</i> (Hewitt, 1916)	3	LC	SAE	B
<i>Ancylotrypa nuda</i> (Hewitt, 1916)	3	LC	SAE	B
<i>Ancylotrypa pretoriae</i> (Hewitt, 1913)	3	LC	SAE	B
9. Family Deinopidae				
<i>Menneus camelus</i> Pocock, 1902	3	LC	SAE	B
10. Family Dictynidae				
<i>Archaeodictyna</i> sp.		NE		
11. Family Entypesidae				
<i>Hermacha mazoena</i> Hewitt, 1915	2	LC	STHE	F
12. Family Eresidae				
<i>Dresserus colsoni</i> Tucker, 1920	3	LC	SAE	F
<i>Stegodyphus africanus</i> (Blackwall, 1866)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Stegodyphus dumicola</i> Pocock, 1898	2	LC	STHE	B
13. Family Gallieniellidae				
<i>Drassodella flava</i> Mbo & Haddad, 2019	3	LC	SAE	B
14. Family Gnaphosidae				
<i>Ammoxenus amphalodes</i> Dippenaar & Meyer, 1980	3	LC	SAE	B
<i>Asemesthes ceresicola</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE	B
<i>Camillina cordifera</i> (Tullgren, 1910)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Camillina maun</i> Platnick & Murphy, 1987	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Drassodes solitarius</i> Purcell, 1907	2	LC	STHE	F
<i>Drassodes splendens</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Ibala arcus</i> (Tucker, 1923)	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Megamyrmaekion transvaalense</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE	F
<i>Nomisia varia</i> (Tucker, 1923)	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Setaphis browni</i> (Tucker, 1923)	0	LC	C	B
<i>Setaphis subtilis</i> (Simon, 1897)	0	LC	C	B
<i>Urozelotes rusticus</i> (L. Koch, 1872)	0	LC	C	B
<i>Xerophaeus aurariarum</i> Purcell, 1907	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Zelotes corrugatus</i> (Purcell, 1907)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Zelotes frenchi</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Zelotes fuliginus</i> (Purcell, 1907)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Zelotes lavus</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Zelotes natalensis</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Zelotes sclateri</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Zelotes scrutatus</i> (O.P.-Cambridge, 1872)	1	LC	AE	B
15. Family Hersiliidae				
<i>Hersilia sericea</i> Pocock, 1898	1	LC	AE	B *
<i>Hersilia setifrons</i> Lawrence, 1928	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Tyrotama australis</i> (Simon, 1893)	2	LC	STHE	B
16. Family Idiopidae				
<i>Ctenolophus fenoulheti</i> Hewitt, 1913	3	LC	SAE	F
<i>Galeosoma planiscutatum</i> Hewitt, 1919	3	LC	SAE	F
17. Family Linyphiidae				
<i>Agyneta habra</i> (Locket, 1968)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Microlinyphia sterilis</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	0	LC	C	B
<i>Tybaertiella krugeri</i> (Simon, 1894)	1	LC	AE	B

FAMILY	END	CON	CEND	KNOWN SEX
18. Family Lycosidae				
<i>Allocosa tuberculipalpa</i> (Caporiacco, 1940)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Evippomma squamulatum</i> (Simon, 1898)	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Foveosa adunca</i> Russell-Smith, Alderweireldt & Jocqué, 2007	3	LC	SAE	B
<i>Hippasa australis</i> Lawrence, 1927	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Pardosa crassipalpis</i> Purcell, 1903	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Proevippa albiventris</i> (Simon, 1898)	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Proevippa fascicularis</i> (Purcell, 1903)	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Trabea purcelli</i> Roewer, 1951	1	LC	AE	B
19. Family Migidae				
<i>Moggridgea paucispina</i> Hewitt, 1916	3	LC	SAE	F
20. Family Oecobiidae				
<i>Oecobius navus</i> Blackwall, 1859	0	LC	C	B
<i>Paroecobius nicolaii</i> Wunderlich, 1995	4	DD	SAE	B
<i>Uroecobius ecribellatus</i> Kullmann & Zimmermann, 1976	3	LC	SAE	B
21. Family Oonopidae				
<i>Dysderina speculifera</i> Simon, 1907	2	LC	STHE	B
22. Family Oxyopidae				
<i>Hamataliwa rostrifrons</i> (Lawrence, 1928)	2	LC	STHE	F
<i>Oxyopes affinis</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Oxyopes bothai</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE	F
<i>Oxyopes flavipalpis</i> (Lucas, 1858)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Oxyopes haggi</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Oxyopes jacksoni</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Oxyopes longispinosus</i> Lawrence, 1938	3	LC	SAE	B
<i>Peucetia striata</i> Karsch, 1878	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Peucetia transvaalica</i> Simon, 1896	1	LC	AE	B
23. Family Palpimanidae				
<i>Palpimanus transvaalicus</i> Simon, 1893	3	LC	SAE	F
24. Family Philodromidae				
<i>Hirriusa arenacea</i> (Lawrence, 1927)	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Philodromus bigibbus australis</i> Lawrence, 1928	3	LC	SAE	B
<i>Thanatus dorsilineatus</i> Jézéquel, 1964	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Thanatus vulgaris</i> Simon, 1870	0	LC	C	B
<i>Tibellus gerhardi</i> Van den Berg & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1994	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Tibellus hollidayi</i> Lawrence, 1952	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Tibellus minor</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE	B
25. Family Pholcidae				
<i>Quamtana hectori</i> Huber, 2003	3	LC	SAE	B
<i>Smeringopus lotzi</i> Hubert, 2012	3	LC	SAE	B
26. Family Phyxelididae				
<i>Vidole sothoana</i> Griswold, 1990	2	LC	STHE	B
27. Family Pisauridae				
<i>Afropisaura rothiformis</i> (Strand, 1908)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Euprosthénops australis</i> Simon, 1898	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Nilus rossi</i> Pocock, 1902	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Rothus aethiopicus</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE	B

FAMILY	END	CON	CEND	KNOWN SEX
28. Family Prodidomidae				
<i>Theuma elucubata</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE	F
<i>Theuma purcelli</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE	F
<i>Theuma schultzei</i> Purcell, 1908	4	LC	SAE	F
29. Family Salticidae				
<i>Baryphas ahenus</i> Simon, 1902	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Cyrba boveyi</i> Lessert, 1933	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Evarcha flagellaris</i> Haddad & Wesolowska, 2011	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Evarcha prosimilis</i> Wesolowska & Cumming, 2008	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Festucula leroyae</i> Azarkina & Foord, 2014	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Harmochirus luculentus</i> Simon, 1885	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Hasarius adansonii</i> (Audouin, 1826)	0	LC	C	B
<i>Heliophanus charlesi</i> Wesolowska, 2003	3	LC	SAE	B
<i>Heliophanus debilis</i> Simon, 1901	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Heliophanus hastatus</i> Wesolowska, 1986	1	LC	STHE	B
<i>Heliophanus orchestra</i> Simon, 1885	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Heliophanus pistaciae</i> Wesolowska, 2003	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Heliophanus transvaalicus</i> Simon, 1901	3	LC	SAE	B
<i>Hyllus argyrotoxa</i> Simon, 1902	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Hyllus dotatus</i> (Peckham & Peckham, 1903)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Icius insolidus</i> (Wesolowska, 1999)	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Mexcala elegans</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Myrmarachne inflatipalpis</i> Wanless, 1978	1	LC	AE	M
<i>Natta chionogaster</i> (Simon, 1901)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Pellenes bulawayoensis</i> Wesolowska, 2000	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Pellenes geniculatus</i> (Simon, 1868)	0	LC	C	B
<i>Pellenes tharinae</i> Wesolowska, 2006	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Pignus simoni</i> (Peckham & Peckham, 1903)	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Planamarengo bimaculata</i> (Peckham & Peckham, 1903)	3	LC	SAE	B
<i>Pseudicius gracilis</i> Haddad & Wesolowska, 2011	3	LC	SAE	B
<i>Rhene konradi</i> Wesolowska, 2009	4	LC	SAE	B
<i>Stenaelurillus guttiger</i> (Simon, 1901)	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Thyene inflata</i> (Gerstäcker, 1873)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Thyene natalii</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Thyene semiargentea</i> (Simon, 1884)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Thyene thyenioides</i> (Lessert, 1925)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Thyenula aurantiaca</i> (Simon, 1902)	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Tusitala barbata</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1902	1	LC	AE	B
30. Family Selenopidae				
<i>Anyphops bechuanicus</i> (Lawrence, 1940)	3	LC	SAE	B
<i>Anyphops tuckeri</i> (Lawrence, 1940)	3	LC	SAE	F
31. Family Sicariidae				
<i>Hexophthalma hahni</i> (Karsch, 1878)	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Loxosceles simillima</i> Lawrence, 1927	1	LC	AE	B
32. Family Sparassidae				
<i>Eusparassus jaegeri</i> Moradmand, 2013	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Olios correvoni nigrifrons</i> Lawrence, 1928	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Palystes superciliosus</i> L. Koch, 1875	2	LC	STHE	B

FAMILY	END	CON	CEND	KNOWN SEX
<i>Pseudomicrommata longipes</i> (Bösenberg & Lenz, 1895)	1	LC	AE	B
33. Family Tetragnathidae				
<i>Leucauge festiva</i> (Blackwall, 1866)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Leucauge kibonotensis</i> Tullgren, 1910	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Tetragnatha bogotensis</i> Keyserling, 1865	0	LC	C	B
<i>Tetragnatha demissa</i> L. Koch, 1872	0	LC	C	B
34. Family Theraphosidae				
<i>Augacephalus junodi</i> (Simon, 1904)	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Brachionopus pretoriae</i> Purcell, 1904	3	DDT	SAE	F
<i>Ceratogyrus darlingi</i> Pocock, 1897	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Harpactira hamiltoni</i> Pocock, 1902	3	LC	SAE	B
<i>Harpactirella overdijki</i> Gallon, 2010	3	DD	SAE	B
35. Family Theridiidae				
<i>Anelosimus nelsoni</i> Agnarsson, 2006	3	LC	SAE	B
<i>Chorizopella tragardhi</i> Lawrence, 1947	3	LC	SAE	F
<i>Enoplognatha molesta</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1904	3	LC	SAE	B
<i>Episinus bilineatus</i> Simon, 1894	2	LC	STHE	J
<i>Euryopsis episinoides</i> (Walckenaer, 1847)	0	LC	C	B
<i>Latrodectus geometricus</i> C.L. Koch, 1841	0	LC	C	B
<i>Latrodectus renivulvatus</i> Dahl, 1902	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Phycosoma martinae</i> (Roberts, 1983)	0	LC	C	B
<i>Steatoda capensis</i> Hann, 1990	0	LC	C	B
<i>Theridion purcelli</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1904	3	LC	SAE	B
36. Family Thomisidae				
<i>Ansiae tuckeri</i> (Lessert, 1919)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Camaricus nigrotesselatus</i> Simon, 1895	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Diaea puncta</i> Karsch, 1884	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Heriaeus copricola</i> Van Niekerk & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2013	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Heriaeus crassispinus</i> Lawrence, 1942	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Hewittia gracilis</i> Lessert, 1928	1	LC	AE	F
<i>Misumenops rubrodecoratus</i> Millot, 1942	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Monaeses austrinus</i> Simon, 1910	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Monaeses paradoxus</i> Lucas, 1864	0	LC	C	B
<i>Monaeses pustulosus</i> Pavesi, 1895	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Monaeses quadrituberculatus</i> Lawrence, 1927	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Mystaria savannensis</i> Lewis & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2014	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Oxytate argenteooculata</i> (Simon, 1886)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Parabomis martini</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Pherecydes lucinae</i> Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1980	3	LC	SAE	B
<i>Runcinia aethiops</i> (Simon, 1901)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Runcinia depressa</i> Simon, 1906	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Runcinia erythrina</i> Jézéquel, 1964	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Runcinia flavida</i> (Simon, 1881)	0	LC	C	B
<i>Runcinia insecta</i> (L. Koch, 1875)	0	LC	C	B
<i>Stiphropus bisigillatus</i> Lawrence, 1952	2	LC	STHE	M
<i>Synema imitatrix</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Synema nigrotibiale</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE	M

FAMILY	END	CON	CEND	KNOWN SEX
<i>Thomisops melanopes</i> Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1989	3	LC	SAE	B
<i>Thomisus blandus</i> Karsch, 1880	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Thomisus citrinellus</i> Simon, 1875	0	LC	C	B
<i>Thomisus congoensis</i> Comellini, 1957	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Thomisus kalaharinus</i> Lawrence, 1936	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Thomisus scrupeus</i> (Simon, 1886)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Thomisus stenningi</i> Pocock, 1900	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Tmarus africanus</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Tmarus cameliformis</i> Millot, 1942	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Tmarus foliatus</i> Lessert, 1928	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Xysticus fagei</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Xysticus mulleri</i> Lawrence, 1952	2	LC	STHE	F
<i>Xysticus natalensis</i> Lawrence, 1938	2	LC	STHE	B
37. Family Trachelidae				
<i>Afroseto martini</i> (Simon, 1897)	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Fuchibotulus kigelia</i> Haddad & Lyle, 2008	2	LC	STHE	B
38. Family Trochanteriidae				
<i>Platyoides walteri</i> (Karsch, 1886)	1	LC	AE	B
39. Family Uloboridae				
<i>Miagrammopes brevicaudus</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1882	2	LC	STHE	F
<i>Uloborus plumipes</i> Lucas, 1846	0	LC	C	B
40. Family Zodariidae				
<i>Capheris decorata</i> Simon, 1904	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Diores femoralis</i> Jocqué, 1990	3	LC	SAE	B
<i>Diores poweri</i> Tucker, 1920	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Diores recurvatus</i> Jocqué, 1990	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Systemoplacis vandami</i> (Hewitt, 1916)	3	LC	SAE	B